

Theory Of Life

* Introduction:

After reading a brief history of time and tasting life a bit, I got a brilliant idea to write my own thesis on life and try to relate it with Einstein's general relativity & Hawking's cosmos theory. This may seem unpredictable at all but most observations are derived from observing the environment & human life deeply. This theory has some pre assumptions that are made in order to match human life with science so that results are believable and understandable • Proof and all assumptions are given below:

* Assumption 1:

This theory considers human life as whole is a constant -

Harding to modern science universe is ever expanding growing larger | explanation about this was already given in Hawking's book, 'A brief history of time' which was way more ahead than its time and still holds a great value in modern science - Nature as an existential object likes to keep things constant. If things go out of its hand it often reciprocates in the form of tsunamis, large natural calamities etc. (Con Earth), so it also means each change made by you in nature will be destroyed! • so ultimately what you did will turn out to nothing. So if you started from 0, u will eventually end at 0 irrespective of path you take.

* Assumption 2:

Human lives & action here are treated like objects in Universe:

This assumption is made in order to apply theories of GR & Cosmology which if applied to human life directly may be considered as unbelievable or unpredictable .

* Assumption 3:

Here life is considered as a loop not a Straight line in 4D :

There are many theories about human existence from the big bang, to Einstein's theory of General relativity , travelling through cosmos .The most common conclusion one can make out of all of them is that the universe follows a loop with no beginning or ending . Think of it as a bi-cycle's wheel it will only stop when the axis will, But as universe is finite as described by hawking and others, we As well have ending, then again big bang will happen, new axis will come, but still energies in universe will be constant (Dark Action law). So, many lives will be destroyed and created but energies are same so the lives destroyed will be same as created, thus forming a loop.

* Assumption 4:

In many references, life will be treated as form of energy rather than in philosophical terms:

As previously covered, energies are constant in universe, so when a person dies actually he's just converted into different form of energy . In biological terms, & scientific terms if we look at human life from the point of view of the universe, we may notice that a human dies, then breaks up into atoms, fur energy is released in various forms like heat, decomposition . A few portion of energies is blended into ground as nutrient through various means . These nutrients as u know through various sources again reaches to another human being or life form. So if we take life philosophically i for u the conclusion can be that u are still alive but in just a different form of energy .

* Conclusion:

If life is energy, and energy never dies, then finite life is just an illusion , and your existence is eternal in ways you've never imagined . Further of this will be discussed in part 2nd , it will tell how this theory affects our short and long term life .

• About me:

M 16 year old writer is writing this as a thesis in order to explore life and make meanings out of absurdity .